

USING THE CALIFORNIA RED WORM IN DEVELOPING SERUM PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY AGAINST HUMAN DISEASE.

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Annotation: The California red worm is grown on earth in its own quality biohumus, in the development of science, in the determination of virological, immunological, microbiological indicators of its effects, it is based on experiential cultivation and obtaining medicine from it. As an experiment, we can see and observe the example of "Chep" and "Guliston" neighborhoods of Oltinsoy district. A total of 50 low-income citizens from "Chep" and "Guliston" neighborhoods located in Oltinsoy district were recruited and capital funds were allocated for each family citizen. Practical work was carried out in two stages for the preparation of medicine.

Key words: California red worm, Drug preparation stages, First stage, "NURZAM", "AZAMZAR"

Main part: In the first phase, each room was supplied with California red worm and feed. For six months, the California red worm carried out continuous care for humus on a target basis of 50 rooms. The goal is that California red worm biohumus will increase soil fertility, while at the same time serving as a foundation for increasing the productivity of agricultural crops and berries. There are 97 species of worms on earth. Only a few species are suitable for feeding. Worms produce many seeds, 4-5 out of 20 seeds survive. The California red worm is very active and aggressive compared to the common "wild" worm. If he has enough food, he will not leave his home. Its length is up to 99 millimeters, its body diameter is 3-5 millimeters, it spawns every day under favorable conditions. After spawning, it lays an egg capsule (up to 20), and after 14-20 days a new generation is born. Newly born worms reach adulthood after 90 days. one California red worm can give birth to 1,500 worms. In one day and night, about 2,400 worms multiply. This type of worm eats its own weight of organic matter every day. 600 kilograms of biohumus and 100 kilograms of protein-rich biomass are produced from one ton of organic waste. Increases the fertility mass of the soil.

In worms, the process of regeneration is strong, and the process of recovery of the divided pieces is high. Because of this, the fluids extracted from it worked as a medicine for the human body.

Manure, weeds, leaves, tree branches, sawdust, straw, kitchen waste, laundry, aviary, animal waste, paper cardboard, etc. are worm food. Nevertheless, it is necessary to collect manure and sprinkle water for 4-5 days. It is necessary to sprinkle water three times a day in southern regions in hot countries. As a result, the organic matter heats up and decomposes. It is appropriate if the biomass pile is dusted with chalk powder, slaked lime or dolomite flour. Because worms do not like a bitter environment. Worms can be fed both indoors and outdoors. Worms can be fed in seats up to 30-100 thousand.

One ton of humus can be prepared in one seat (2x1m) in a year. 40% of nutritious substrate is used for the life of worms, 60% of biohumus is formed in the form of copromite. close worm biomass is obtained. Seats are built on slightly sloping plots so that rain does not collect and form puddles. It is important to protect the worm especially from bats, they are a fierce enemy.

It doesn't matter what day or month you start worming. The best time is spring, autumn and summer. Worms are sensitive to ammonia and high temperature. For this reason, only fermented and cooled manure can be used for feeding. Other organic waste must also rot.

A domestic rabbit is ready for worm feeding in the last 5-10 days, a horse in 3-4 months, and a cattle after 5-6 months. If there is little food, the worms will die, if there is a lot of food, breathing and gas exchange will be difficult. Always monitor the reproduction and development of worms. should be done. Worms in boxes, balcony. The land is full, it is also possible to build in garages.

Our experimental area is "Chep" and "Guliston" neighborhoods of Oltinsoy district, where along with the cultivation of nutritious biohumus, the California red worm, which is used for human diseases, is cultivated it is separated, fixed, filtered and placed in a drying cabinet. after drying in the oven for 48 hours, the red worm is sifted through a special tool and turned into flour. 12 mg of this sample is taken and placed in a flask, the necessary reagents are added to it and placed in a thermostat. Blood fluid obtained from the gelment is added to the gelment liquid, which is sterilized in the thermostat, and it is centrifuged.

The serum obtained from this sample is subjected to an immunological examination and the level of influence on the human immune system is studied. The basis of this experiment was that we can see that the anti-serum is ready for 11 different diseases in the fight against human diseases and observe the pathological symptoms. This serum "NURZAM" is the most powerful tool for preventing hepatitis-A and hepatitis-B infection in the prevention of viral infectious diseases.

"AZAMZAR" cream ointment was prepared in a laboratory method from a sample taken from the California red worm and is used to prevent skin diseases such as leishmaniasis, vitiligo, psoriasis, and allergic rashes. Hematological indicators have been proven to be 15% higher than statistical data. It became known that the formation of erythrocytes and increase in cellularity in the human organism is regularly high

Experience shows that with the help of earthworms, it is necessary to turn organic substances into biohumus, which can be quickly absorbed by plants. Biohumus contains ten times more plant nutrients. Let's say that if 500 cattle are kept in a livestock farm, the manure produced from them can feed 200 hectares of land. This amount of organic biohumus can be used to feed 1000 hectares. 2 years ago in the "Chep" and "Guliston" neighborhoods of Oltinsoy district, pilot experiments were carried out.

Conclusion: Serum and cream ointments against eleven different diseases were developed from cultured specimens of California red worm, and sustainable mechanisms for human health were established. In order to prevent hemolytic hematological anemia, a wide field was opened for the stimulation of erythropoiesis and production using technological resources was launched.

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